

ORION | Trapezium

Eastern Time = EDT = UTC – 4 hrs

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A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

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ORION is an amateur science and astronomy group that was founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville, and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and amateur astronomy in East Tennessee. We are accordingly closely associated with and support the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) through hosting their public events, sharing our knowledge of the skies using a variety of telescopes, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs at the observatory. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science with people from all walks of life.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20.00; student discounts are available.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

Vice President and Program Chair:

David Fields

Secretary: Noah Frere

Treasurer: Bob Edwards w/ Noah Frere

Trapezium Editor: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach and Oak Ridge Star

Parties: Owen Hoffman

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly Monday ORION meeting, to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

Trapezium includes summaries of the recent activities of the Society, discussions of recent developments and discoveries in astronomy likely to be of interest to ORION members, promotes communication between the membership, and highlights activities sponsored by ORION, notably those that involve public outreach at TAO. It also acts as a forum for the Society, publishes commentaries on aspects of space science and astronomy, and provides "gallery space" for recent work by ORION astrophotographers, especially for images captured at TAO.

Page Three Astronomy

A NEW FEATURE

To encourage interest in and appreciation of astronomy, a striking new celestial image will be posted here monthly in the Trapezium. We hope to feature images captured by ORION members, as well as art of relevance to astronomy.

Our first such image shows the famous Sombrero peculiar galaxy M104 in the constellation Virgo, distance ca. 9.6 megaparsecs, visual magnitude 8.0, date 10 Apr 2019, total exposure time 20 minutes. This image was captured at the Lost Ridge Observatory (LRO) located near Clinton, Tennessee.

President's Message – Don Spong

It was good to see a number of you out at Tamke-Allan on the evening of May 21. Although there were initially a few clouds around, the skies cleared up for some good observing (see my images below, pp.18-22). We had both visual and imaging astronomers present and this was probably one of the larger groups we've had in several months. Thanks to David Fields for opening things up for us and to Ted for pushing for the May 21st date. We'll hope for clear skies and more opportunities like this through the summer months. As you may be aware, there has recently been a new supernova identified in the Pinwheel Galaxy (M101). This is designated as SN 2023ixf and was actually discovered by an amateur astronomer, Koichi Itagaki on May 19, 2023 from Yamagata, Japan. It is the closest to earth and one of the largest/brightest of all supernovas seen in a decade. It should be visible to amateur astronomers for several months – worth getting out and searching for next time we have clear skies.

ET Message received from Mars. Can we analyze it with AI? David Fields

Vice President's Vision, June 2023

Intro:

Might we use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to analyze complex radio signals, such as those that might have been composed by an advanced Extra-Terrestrial (ET) Civilization?

Maybe. I've no doubt that our security agencies use advanced computers for code-breaking. And I've no doubt that many people have considered how to compose and interpret possible AI signals. We (NASA) sent a signal to ET on the famous Voyager Gold Disk.

<https://voyager.jpl.nasa.gov/golden-record/>

Now we have access to an entirely new tool that might help us communication with ET – a class of AI programs that interpret questions (called prompts) based of years of internet records, and respond in text. These programs all stem from the release last year of ChatGPT.

<https://chat.openai.com/>

The obvious question that arises is whether ChatGPT can analyze alien (ET) signals.

Background:

We ORION members need to get to better know each other. Bob Edwards has suggested that each ORION member gives a 10-minute talk about him or herself. Ted Barnes told about us about his background along with his ORION presentation. And he is starting to feature ORION members in the Trapezium (see Rob Fowler's article in this issue).

So my background includes some interesting computer adventures, early AI of a sort. There was a lot of antenna and receiver work and radio signal analysis, some H1 (hydrogen) signal captures, Jove listening, VLF studies with SuperSID, some research and some SARA presentations. Then there was the RASDR receiver development with Bogdan, Paul, Carl, and Marcus. For now, I'm working toward a cubesat (TAOsat) (with Rob, Carl, Makhan, Dave, and Bogdan) that will open up VLF signal reception and on-board satellite computer processing to students and others. We've flown some of our instruments on drones and balloons. This is great for teaching Astronomy at Roane State, and we like to show them some of our astronomy at Tamke-Allan Observatory.

I also worked with computers at ORNL in an early AI project. I built some computer codes running physics-based models that simulated river sediment transport, watershed models of hydrologic systems, atmospheric movements, and radionuclide pollution transport in the environment. Then I programmed the computer to compare measurements with predictions to determine some unknown things. The computer codes were useful - solutions were the result of an automated exploratory process, not a simple calculation.

I recently read "The Three-Body Problem", which included a (fictional) account of an ET message receipt. The book was great, with an immensely complex plot. It was followed by a Chinese-produced movie "Three-Body", which was a wonderful production. A feature of the plot development was computer analysis of SETI signals.

Can we use the latest AI tools (ChatGPT) to analyze, identify and decode ET signals?

The latest "AI" thing is ChatGPT, and I wondered if it could be used to analyze an ET signal. ChatGPT is a conversational AI and is linguistic in the interface (this frustrates me a lot). Nevertheless, there is much going on in the background. Can we input an unknown signal? I investigated that.

ESA's ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter, in orbit around Mars [not extra-solar, of course], transmitted on Wednesday May 24 an encoded message to Earth that acted as a simulation of a message from another civilization. The message was detected by the Allen Telescope Array (ATA) in California, the Green Bank Telescope (GBT) in West Virginia and the Medicina Radio Astronomical Observatory in Italy.

So, can I decode this "ET" signal just sent from Mars orbit? Could I use advanced AI tools?

On May 21, I learned of the upcoming transmission and it occurred to me that I might be able to upload this message to an advanced AI which could help decode it. To that end, I tested a small part of the idea using ChatGPT (<https://chat.openai.com/>). Here are the results from my first test, which (to my surprise) demonstrate multi-level linguistic processing and decoding:

I presented this question (called a prompt) to the AI computer:

Act as a SETI researcher and interpret the following received signal:-.. .-.. ---

ChatGPT responded this way:

As a SETI researcher, I can help you interpret the received signal. The signal you provided is a sequence of Morse code. Morse code is a communication system that uses dots (.) and dashes (-) to represent letters and numbers.

The received signal ".... .-.. .-.. ---" translates to the following letters in Morse code:

H - E - . L - .-.. L - .-.. O - ---

Putting it all together, the received signal ".... .-.. .-.. ---" corresponds to the word "HELLO" in Morse code.

If you have any further signals or need assistance with any other SETI-related queries, feel free to ask!

That surprised me -- ChatGPT in several ways performed beyond what I had expected. As I hinted at, communication with ChatGPT is language-based. I experimented more and found that I could upload limited serial data, but so far, not much more. I've engaged ChatGPT in dialogues about entering data.

On May 25, I listened to a discussion of the ESA orbiter transmission, presented by ESA and Green Bank people:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zgQq36IR-Lk>

The intro to that YouTube discussion pointed me here:

A Sign in Space website: <https://asignin.space/>

Join the Discord: <https://discord.com/invite/2upxzmZkqY>

Download the data at Filecoin: <https://destor.io/seti> or on BTL:

https://bldata.berkeley.edu/A_Sign_in...

After listening to that YouTube discussion, as of 13:45h on May 25, this was the situation:

- The Mars ET signal (maybe 17 terabytes per telescope) arriving at X-band (about 8 GHz) was recorded on May 24 by 3+ large telescopes.
- These terabytes of data were compressed into (4) files in "immutable" format, each file about 5 GB in size.
- I downloaded one of these files and probably need to determine a parsing length, then identify delimiters and unique characters, and search for identifiable character sequences. The format is for me unusual, but apparently can be handled in Python, C++, Gnu radio, *etc.*

But I have other things to do and don't have software ready for such a task. And I don't know yet how to present a large file to ChatGPT for analysis. I'm still thinking about it though.

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Our monthly meetings generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited presentation and discussion
- Astrotechnology
- Astrophotography

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm, on the third Monday of the month. There will usually be time available at the beginning of the meeting for announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9 pm. Please plan to stay until the end of the meeting. We hopefully will all enjoy the astrophotography, as well as discussions of techniques used in capturing astronomical images.

Information about ORION & TAO

May be found at the following URLs:

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

Where is TAO?

35° 49' 57" N, 84° 37' 04" W; Alt. 324 m

Would you like to contribute to Trapezium?

Proposed topics for Trapezium may be discussed with the Editor, Dr. Ted Barnes, by email at *ted dot barnes2 at yahoo dot com*.

Title: RamSat: A mentor's view of STEM success built on NASA's Cubesat Launch Initiative**Speaker: Dr. Peter Thornton (ORNL)****Distinguished R&D Staff, Section Head for Earth Systems Science, Director of Climate Change Science Institute**

Bio: Peter is a Distinguished Scientist at Oak Ridge National Laboratory. He studies biogeochemistry of land, coastal, and aquatic ecosystems, and incorporates that knowledge into models to improve predictions of future climate. His research spans spatial scales from plots to the global Earth system. A special focus of his research is the coupling of the biotic and abiotic cycling of nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, which limit growth and metabolism of plants and microbes. Peter is a mentor to several technology projects within the Oak Ridge Public Schools, and serves as a board member for the Oak Ridge Public Schools Education Foundation.

Abstract: A group of students and mentors from Robertsville Middle School in Oak Ridge, Tennessee has carried out a successful cubesat mission, named RamSat (after the Robertsville Rams). The mission was built on NASA's Cubesat Launch Initiative (CSLI), and has involved a close collaboration of students, educators, and administrators at Oak Ridge Public Schools with scientists, engineers, and subject area experts from the surrounding community. We present a history of the mission with a focus on the lessons

Title: RamSat: A mentor's view of STEM success built on NASA's Cubesat Launch Initiative

Abstract (cont.): learned as our team of mentors and educators engaged numerous classrooms of students over seven years, and as we interacted with NASA, launch service providers, vendors, communities of experts, and the local interested public. This presentation focuses on the mentors' perspective. With little or no formal educational training we learned-while-doing by observing the classroom instructors and iterating our approach to provide a range of opportunities for the students, while aiming for technical success of the mission. We reflect on what worked and what didn't, and how the whole student-educator-mentor team met and overcame the challenges of a first space mission. We offer suggestions for other middle or high school teams contemplating a cubesat mission, in hopes that our experience might help inform a range of similar STEM activities. We highlight the importance of the open-source science community in leveraging the efforts of our small team to help reach a truly global audience.

Meeting Info: 7 pm Monday 19 June 2023, Roane State Community College, Coffey / McNalley Bldg., City Room (A-111).

A Zoom session will be open at the link

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or

<https://bit.ly/42apGxX> Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

June 19 ORION Presentation:

RamSat

Summary:

The Robertsville Middle School CubeSat (Oak Ridge's first satellite, dubbed RamSat for the school's mascot) began its construction in the 2015-2016 school year after Robertsville became the first middle school selected by NASA's CubeSat Launch Initiative (CSLI) program. RamSat is a two-unit CubeSat, with dimensions of 20 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm. Its primary mission was to take pictures of the forests around Gatlinburg, which were destroyed by wildfires in 2016.

RamSat has an educational commission, to develop a middle school STEM curriculum. The mission was wholly designed and carried out by students, teachers, and mentors.

Launched on June 3, 2021 from NASA's Kennedy Space Center as part of SpaceX Commercial Resupply Service (CRS-22) to the International Space Station, RamSat was deployed into low earth orbit on June 14, and successfully down-linked numerous images. RamSat transmitted a telemetry beacon every 60 seconds, together with additional telemetry data. It was a great success for the Robertsville students. RamSat deorbited on Oct. 11, 2022.

In January 2023, a group of Oak Ridge High School students accomplished a remarkable goal – they presented a poster about their own research to the world’s largest conference for Earth and space sciences. The students – **Hudson Reynolds, Laurel Hetrick, Joe Blair, Adler Keehn, Jonathan Bonamarte, Odelia Kneiser, Brandon Bonamarte, and Boru Kneiser** – traveled to New Orleans in December to participate in the 2021 Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union.

The students worked together to perform the research and design their poster. The conference is intended for scientists to present new results from their own research, and this team rose to the challenge by gathering and analyzing data from a small satellite that they themselves had designed, built, delivered for launch, and operated in orbit. They had begun work on their space mission, named RamSat, as part of a NASA STEM class at Robertsville Middle School. With RamSat’s launch this past June, the group has been able to receive data from the satellite at their radio ground station in the RMS STEM classroom, with additional data gathered by amateur radio enthusiasts around the world.

RamSat experienced extreme variations in temperature as it orbited the Earth, and the students studied how small changes in the orbit at different times of year led to large changes in temperatures measured on RamSat’s solar panels and inside its electronic components. They were able to accurately predict, months in advance, the occurrence of a strong heating event that took place at the time of the poster presentation in mid-December.

The student team was responsible for all aspects of their research and presentation, and on December 16th they were all present in the vast poster hall at the New Orleans convention center, with thousands of graduate students, professors, and professional researchers to share what they had learned with their fellow scientists. Dozens of people stopped by to hear about the RamSat mission and to discuss the students' research findings, and the students in turn had opportunities to visit with many other researchers studying topics as diverse as colonization of other planets to making biofuels from algae.

These students gained a first-hand appreciation for the collaborative approach that drives much of modern scientific research. They also made great strides in learning how to communicate the results of their research to an audience of curious non-experts. In all of their preparations, and in their enthusiastic engagement at the conference, these students exemplified and did honor to the intellectual spirit of the Oak Ridge Schools. Congratulations to the RamSat student team for an outstanding performance!

ORION Last Month:

Last month's presentation, on 15 May 2023, was by ORION President Don Spong, who discussed his experiences at the North East Astronomy Forum (NEAF), Suffern, New York, 15-16 April 2023. NEAF is the largest amateur astronomy meeting in North America, and Don had planned to attend in earlier years but this was not possible because NEAF was cancelled due to Covid-19 in 2020-2022.

In his description of the 2023 NEAF, Don noted the camaraderie with other participants, the impressive displays by the major manufacturers of telescopes and cameras for amateurs, as well as the availability of many interesting "gadgets" such as eyepieces with diffraction gratings for stellar spectroscopy, small red warning lights for tripod feet, and a small pinhole light source for collimation. In addition there were presentations by professional astronomers and astronauts, which are available to online viewers. (See last month's ORION presentation description.) Don strongly encourages those who have the opportunity to visit NEAF in future.

Visitors Kirsten and daughter Caroline watching the awards ceremony.

Don receives his speaker's cup from David.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision. Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

- Conjunction** – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.
- Constellation** – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.
- Diffuse Nebula** – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.
- Double Star** – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").
- Ecliptic** – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.
- Elongation** – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.
- Galaxy** – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.
- Globular Star Cluster** – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.
- Light Year (ly)** – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.
- Magnitude** – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.
- Open Star Cluster** – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.
- Opposition** – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.
- Planetary Nebula** – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.
- Universal Time (UT)** – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

- Aql** • Brightest star in Aquila. Name means "the flying eagle". Dist=16.8 ly.
- Boo** • Orange, giant K star. Name means "bear watcher". Dist=36.7 ly.
- Cep** • Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5.366 days. Mag 6 companion.
- Cyg** • Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supernovae. Dist=1,400±200 ly.
- Her** • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.1 & 3.9 over 90 days. Mag 5.4 companion.
- Lyr** • The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly.
- Sco** • Red, supergiant star. Name means "fowl of Mars". Dist=135.9 ly.
- UMi** • The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist=433ly.
- Vir** • Latin name means "ear of wheat" and shown held in Virgo's left hand. Dist=250 ly.

Easily Seen with Binoculars

- Aql** • Bright Cepheid variable. Mag varies between 3.6 & 4.5 over 7.166 days. Dist=1,200 ly.
- CvN** • Easy to find in binoculars. Might be glimpsed with the naked eye.
- Cep** • Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days.
- Com** • Coma Berenices. 80 mag 5-6 stars in 5 deg. Dist=283 ly. Age=600 million years.
- Cyg** • Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days.
- Cyg** • May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist=900 ly.
- Dra** • Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly.
- Her** • Best globular in northern skies. Discovered by Halley in 1714. Dist=23,000 ly.
- Her** • Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars.
- Lyr** • Famous Double Double. Binoculars show a double star. High power reveals each a double.
- Lyr** • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
- Oph** • Close to the brighter M10. Dist=18,000 ly.
- Oph** • 3 degrees from the fainter M12. Both may be glimpsed in binoculars. Dist=14,000 ly.
- Oph** • Large, scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
- Oph** • Scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
- Sgr** • Lagoon Nebula. Bright nebula bisected by a dark lane. Dist=5,200 ly.
- Sgr** • Bright cluster located about 6 deg N of "teapot's" lid. Dist=1,900 ly.
- Sgr** • A spectacular globular star cluster. Telescope will show stars. Dist=10,000 ly.
- Sco** • A close globular. May just be visible without optical aid. Dist=7,000 ly.
- Sco** • Butterfly Cluster. 30+ stars in 7x binoculars. Dist=1,960 ly.
- Sco** • Superb open cluster. Visible to the naked eye. Age=260 million years. Dist=780 ly.
- Ser** • Fine globular star cluster. Telescope will reveal individual stars. Dist=25,000 ly.
- UMa** • Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.
- Vir** • Coathanger asterism or "Broccchi's Cluster". Not a true star cluster. Dist=218 to 1,140 ly.

Telescopic Objects

- Boo** • Red giant star (mag 2.5) with a blue-green mag 4.9 companion. Sep=2.8". Difficult to split.
- CvN** • Compact nearby face-on spiral galaxy. Dist=15 million ly.
- CvN** • Whirlpool Galaxy. First recognised to have spiral structure. Dist=25 million ly.
- Com** • Black-Eye Galaxy. Discovered by J.E. Bode in 1775 - "a small, nebulous star".
- Cyg** • Beautiful double star. Contrasting colours of orange and blue-green. Sep=34.4".
- Cyg** • Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist=11.4 ly. Sep=28.4".
- Del** • Appear yellow & white. Mags 4.3 & 5.2. Dist=100 ly. Struve 2725 double in same field.
- Lyr** • Eclipsing binary. Mag varies between 3.3 & 4.3 over 12.940 days. Fainter mag 7.2 blue star.
- Lyr** • Ring Nebula. Magnificent object. Smoke-ring shape. Dist=4,100 ly.
- Sgr** • Elongated star cluster. Telescope required to show stars. Dist=2,100 ly.
- Sgr** • Trifid Nebula. A telescope shows 3 dust lanes trisecting nebula. Dist=5,200 ly.
- Sgr** • A fine and impressive cluster. Dist=4,200 ly.
- Sgr** • Omega Nebula. Contains the star cluster NGC 6618. Dist=4,900 ly.
- Sct** • Wild Duck Cluster. Resembles a globular through binoculars. V-shaped. Dist=5,600 ly.
- Ser** • Eagle Nebula. Requires a telescope of large aperture. Dist=8,150 ly.
- UMa** • Superficial spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
- UMa** • Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller.
- Vir** • Superficial galaxy with supermassive black hole at its core. Dist=53.5 million ly.
- Vir** • Superb pair of mag 3.5 yellow-white stars. Orbit=169 years. At their closest in 2005.
- Vir** • Dumbbell Nebula. Large, twin-lobed shape. Most spectacular planetary. Dist=975 ly.
- Vul** • ✦

Supernova Report: FLASH! SN 2023ixf in M101

A very bright new type II supernova was recently reported in the relatively nearby “Pinwheel” galaxy M101, in Ursa Major. This SN, now known as 2023ixf, was discovered by prolific amateur astronomer Koichi Itagaki at 2023/05/19.727 UT, when it was at magnitude 14.9. The discovery image, shown below, is from the Purdue SN site. Subsequently 2023ixf brightened by about three magnitudes in one day, and appears to have peaked around magnitude 11.0 at 2023/05/24.0 UT. The previous brightest SN in 2023 was 2023bee, a type Ia in Hydra which only reached magnitude 13.2.

Extragalactic supernovae (SN or SNe) are in many ways ideal targets for amateur astronomers. They can appear anywhere in the sky at any time, and are of considerable interest to the public. The discovery rate of new SNe is quite high, due in part to automatic discovery facilities; in 2022, 19297 SNe were reported, just over 50/day. The brighter ones typically reach magnitudes of 13 to 14, so they are accessible visually in a midrange telescope. They usually remain visible for a period of weeks to months. The most common types of supernovae are Ia (accretion-ignition) and II (core collapse).

Supernova Report (cont.)

A summary table of the brightest currently accessible supernovae follows.

SN	mag		type	host	RA	Dec	Con
2023ixf	10.8		IIL	M101	14 03 38.6	+54 18 42	Com
2023dzc	14.8	*	Ia	anon.	06 11 58.3	+58 48 58	Cam
AT2023iez	14.9		unk	LEDA 1311625	13 07 00.6	+06 59 21	Vir
2023gft	15.1		Ia	MCG-1-54-16	21 26 01.3	-03 47 54	Cep
2023gfo	15.3		II	NGC 4995	13 09 39.7	-07 50 12	Vir
2023esp	15.3	*	IIIn	anon.	06 46 53.8	+15 35 54	Gem
2023axu	15.3	*	II	NGC 2283	06 45 55.3	-18 13 53	CMa
2023hlu	15.5	*	II	UGC 12308	23 01 15.7	+14 20 40	Peg
2023ijd	16.0		II	NGC 4568	12 36 32.5	+11 13 20	Com
2023hrn	16.1		Ia	NGC 3535	11 08 35.1	+04 48 52	Leo
2023hsb	16.1		Ia-91T	MCG+9-31-13	18 59 39.3	+55 22 54	Dra
2023bee	16.2		Ia	NGC 2708	08 56 11.6	-03 19 32	Hya
2023foa	16.2	*	Ia	UGC 10678	17 03 59.3	+24 11 11	Her
2023dea	16.3	*	Ia	UGC 2822	03 42 04.7	+41 08 14	Per
2023aub	16.3	*	II	IC 4219	13 18 31.1	-31 37 50	Cen
AT2023hrm	16.5		unk	M31	00 42 44.9	+41 15 03	And
AT2023gcl	16.5		unk	NGC7656	23 24 33.8	-19 03 24	Aqu
2023jri	16.5		II	UGC 12639	23 30 27.1	+30 13 11	Peg
2023eob	16.5	*	Ia	LEDA 3848414	15 31 53.2	-31 10 12	Lup

Table: The current 19 brightest SNe with an identified host galaxy, with a cut on Dec > -35 deg for possible visibility in the Northern Hemisphere. An asterisk * denotes magnitude data over a month old. Updated 6 Jun 2023.

Supernova Report (cont.)

This is the SNe data from the previous page, sorted by RA to assist observers.

SN	mag	type	host	RA	Dec	Con
AT2023hrm	16.5	unk	M31	00 42 44.9	+41 15 03	And
2023dea	16.3	* la	UGC 2822	03 42 04.7	+41 08 14	Per
2023dzc	14.8	* la	anon.	06 11 58.3	+58 48 58	Cam
2023axu	15.3	* II	NGC 2283	06 45 55.3	-18 13 53	CMa
2023esp	15.3	* IIn	anon.	06 46 53.8	+15 35 54	Gem
2023bee	16.2	la	NGC 2708	08 56 11.6	-03 19 32	Hya
2023hrn	16.1	la	NGC 3535	11 08 35.1	+04 48 52	Leo
2023ijd	16.0	II	NGC 4568	12 36 32.5	+11 13 20	Com
AT2023iez	14.9	unk	LEDA 1311625	13 07 00.6	+06 59 21	Vir
2023gfo	15.3	II	NGC 4995	13 09 39.7	-07 50 12	Vir
2023aub	16.3	* II	IC 4219	13 18 31.1	-31 37 50	Cen
2023ixf	10.8	IIL	M101	14 03 38.6	+54 18 42	Com
2023eob	16.5	* la	LEDA 3848414	15 31 53.2	-31 10 12	Lup
2023foa	16.2	* la	UGC 10678	17 03 59.3	+24 11 11	Her
2023hsb	16.1	la-91T	MCG+9-31-13	18 59 39.3	+55 22 54	Dra
2023gft	15.1	la	MCG-1-54-16	21 26 01.3	-03 47 54	Cep
2023hlu	15.5	* II	UGC 12308	23 01 15.7	+14 20 40	Peg
AT2023gcl	16.5	unk	NGC7656	23 24 33.8	-19 03 24	Aqu
2023jri	16.5	II	UGC 12639	23 30 27.1	+30 13 11	Peg

Table: The current 19 brightest SNe with an identified host galaxy, with a cut on Dec > -35 deg for possible visibility in the Northern Hemisphere. An asterisk * denotes magnitude data over a month old. Updated 6 Jun 2023.

Regular updates of supernova data may be found on several sites, for example <https://www.physics.purdue.edu/brightsupernovae/>, which provided the data summarized here. This topic will be updated in successive issues, and any new, especially notable information regarding SNe will be presented here as well.

Observatory Way

David Fields

The May 21 Star Party at TAO

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. The sign is on the left as you turn from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

We had a great Star Party on May 21 (with new moon, clear skies, charged batteries, lots of visitors, etc.). Don Spong and Ted Barnes are doing a great job reporting their astrophotography results (see your **June Trapezium**), but there was much more happening. We had some great astronomy/physics conversations and did initial investigations of the feasibility of Zoom broadcasts from TAO.

Another time, we'll discuss the food (well, OK, tasty ham and cheese sandwiches, crunchy popcorn, artisanal bread, lots of cookies and desert things, coffee, just from memory). Several new scope setups were tried and tested – most worked out well. And the weather was phenomenally comfortable. I took a few candid photos of people doing their astronomy things for the evening, and hope you'll enjoy them:

Astrophotography – Don Spong

The following three images were made on May 21, 2023 at Tamke-Allan. My processed images are paired with annotated, plate-solved images obtained from passing these through astrometry.net.

The Needle Galaxy (NGC 4565) – This edge-on spiral galaxy in the constellation Coma Berenices was discovered by William Herschel in 1785. Due to its brightness (10.4) it's not hard to capture the general shape. It requires longer focal length and resolution to capture the granularity in the central dust lane and the central bulge. This galaxy is about 50 million light-years (Mly) away.

Markarian's Chain – This is a region of the sky in Virgo that is covered with galaxies. The main group of about 20 galaxies (mostly elliptical) is within a triangular region of about 2° on a side. These were identified in a 1961 paper by Benjamin Markarian, who postulated that they were a gravitationally connected group.

Here I've only captured part of the chain since I had my GoTo system center the image on M84. In the future I hope to get a more complete image of the chain by centering the image more on NGC 4435. This image was made using a hyperstar attachment on my Celestron; this replaces the secondary mirror, giving an f1.9 and a wider field of view.

Markarian's Chain

IC 3355 NGC 4435 IC 3393
NGC 4438 IC 3388

NGC 3370

NGC 4406 / M 81 NGC 4425

IC 3280

IC 3235

NGC 4374 / M 84 NGC 4387 NGC 4407 IC 3363

NGC 4374 / M 84

NGC 4448

NGC 4388 NGC 4388 NGC 4431

IC 3246

IC 3279

IC 3349

IC 3354

IC 3315

IC 3311

IC 3258

NGC 4306

NGC 4305

NGC 4367

IC 3331

The Paperkite Galaxy (NGC 4762) – This galaxy is in the constellation Virgo, and is at RA: 12h 52m 56.05s, Dec: +11° 13' 51", Distance: 58 Mly, Apparent magnitude 11.12. This is the Sky-Watcher Target of the Month for May. It is an edge-on lenticular galaxy consisting of a central bulge, a bar, a thick disk, and an outer ring. The disc is asymmetric and warped, possibly due to a past merger with a smaller galaxy. Spectral line emissions indicate that the central region is an energetic active galactic nucleus of the LINER category.

Astrophotography at TAO / 21 May 2023 by Ted Barnes

`Twas a dark and stormy night. No, `twas worse, on a stormy night we would have cancelled the observing session outright. In this case, although the Clear Sky Chart had been predicting promising observing weather for TAO on Sunday 21 May for several days, on the drive towards Kingston I noticed a rather thick haze in the sky, and the distant ridges appeared grey in outline. It looked like Los Angeles. We had a serious problem with smoke.

I had made several improvements in equipment since April. First, I learned how to set power management on my refurbished Win 10 Pro laptop to a max CPU load (85% was recommended online) so there would be no more catastrophic unwarned shutdowns due to CPU overheating. That seems to have worked! A live core temperature readout app, Core Temp v 1.18, has also been very helpful. I also bought an S-shaped metal stand that raises the laptop well above my work surface, so cooling airflow is not restricted by having a small gap.

Due to light traffic I arrived at TAO 20 minutes before my planned 7:15 pm, so I had a wait outside the fence. Why don't we install an electronic lock with a passcode (call it a security measure) for trusted guests who arrive early? OK, never mind. I started setting up, and according to my notes was finished by 8:50 pm. (Nominal sunset at TAO was 8:42 pm.) It's true, setup does take me about 1.5 hrs. This time I brought a hamper with ham and cheese rolls for Sunny the Astrodog, who had previously expressed considerable interest in this subject. He happily accepted two. Humans were of course also welcome. The next stage in setting up is alignment, which requires pointing the OTA towards Polaris. But where was Polaris? Even in binoculars it was not visible, evidently the smoke and haze in the atmosphere was even worse than I had thought, and was hiding Polaris.

Moon: We did have an attractive crescent moon low in the West, and David Fields had asked if I could try to capture that, so around 9:40 pm I deferred my alignment plans and slewed down to the moon "by hand," and captured a series of single images with a gain of 450 and exposures of 1, 2, 4 and 8 ms, and 1/60 sec. The longer exposures have an overexposed outer region, so my favorite was 1 ms. The first such 1 ms image, shown on the next page, was taken at 9:43 pm Eastern. The moon was already quite low in the sky (Alt. 13.7 deg, Azi. 293.9 deg). This image is approximately the correct orientation of the moon as seen from TAO at that time. Three craters near the lower limb which are clearly visible in the image, Adams, Legendre and Phillips, are indicated. For reference, the lunar coordinates of Legendre are 28.9 deg S and 70.0 deg E.

Crescent moon at TAO
9:43 pm Eastern 21 May 2023
Alt. 13.7 deg, Azi. 293.9 deg

Adams

Legendre

Phillips

By around 10:00 pm I could finally see Polaris, and used it with my OTA's laser for rough polar alignment. I guessed where the NCP was relative to Polaris, and was wrong by about a degree; this step needs work. This was followed by Manual Alignment, with a change of my stored current location to that of TAO, and the addition of about 8 regular alignment stars, ending with Alkaid (last star in the tail of Ursa Major). This was a deliberate choice because it ended near M101, a bright galaxy on my list to image.

M101: After two minutes of a live stack of M101, 15x8sG540, I checked my cumulative raw image and saw no indication of spiral arms, even with the high gain of 540. This was terrible; the hazy sky was beating out even M101. What to do? Was my focus poor? I returned to Alkaid and sharpened my focus and then tried to return to M101, but the OTA instead headed South. What??? The meridian at that time was in the tail of Ursa Major, and I think crossing it repeatedly was giving my equatorial mount very strange ideas for moves. (The heart-stopping mount manoeuvres called “meridian flips” can result in tangled cables.) For technical reasons I was using a fresh instance of SharpCap with a new user name and account on my Win 10 Pro laptop “Sapphire,” and hadn't yet set all my usual defaults, like telling it to go easy on meridian flips unless it is way across the line. Since the mount control program CPWI was first pointing the OTA near the zenith (vertical) and then sending it somewhere crazy (far South), I hit the CPWI panic button to stop OTA movement. Now my usual CPWI sky map was gone, and I had to struggle to get something reasonable back on the screen. Don't panic!

Supernova 2023dtz: About that time I decided to stop fooling around, cut my losses, and to go straight to one of the two supernovae I STILL had at the top of my list of things to image. I had *never* imaged a supernova before 21 May 2023, and had listed the 16 brightest accessible ones in the May Trapezium, so this was a great opportunity. Just do it! And these supernovae are just stars in appearance (albeit moderately faint ones, like 15th or 16th magnitude), so maybe the image would punch through this hazy sky. The first SN on my list, almost the brightest in the sky, was approaching a 10:51 pm meridian crossing, so to heck with that. I instead went to the second SN, 2023dtz in Coma Berenices, and began a live stack at 10:55 pm. I chose 4s frames at a high camera gain of 540 and stacked 240 frames, finishing this 16 min exposure at 11:18 pm. (The additional time was for pauses when people turned on vehicle lights.) The post-processed image of 2023dtz in its home galaxy NGC 4611 appears on the following page, and is a quite reasonable first attempt.

Two good things I had done in preparation for taking this SN image were to 1) assemble a library of dark frames the day before; SharpCap uses darks as a reference to remove stuck-on primary color pixels from the image, and 2) unlike my April TAO trip, in May I remembered to plug in the camera cooler. The log files tell me that the camera sensor was at a nice cool -14.8C ~ +5.4F during this exposure.

Supernova 2023dtz (type Ia)
Spiral galaxy NGC 4611 (dist *ca.* 90 Mpc, mag = 14.7)
in Coma Berenices

SN 2023dtz is visible just to the right of the nucleus of NGC 4611. The g-magnitudes of the visible field stars, taken from Gaia EDR3 data, are given next to each star's image. (One of the field stars is 20th mag, so maybe this part of the sky wasn't so bad after all.) A comparison of 2023dtz with the field stars suggests that as of the date of the image, 21 May 2023, the supernova may have fallen by about one magnitude from the 15.9 that was reported on 25 Apr 2023. (In the 4 May SN chart given in the May Trapezium issue it had already fallen below mag 16.4, and so does not appear in that table.)

Regarding the host galaxy itself, NGC 4611 is a type Sbc spiral with a redshift of $z = 0.0204$, corresponding to a distance of about 90 Mpc or 290 Mly. The NED database quotes a g-magnitude for NGC 4611 of 14.7.

M101 (redux): Now, back to M101. Recall that I had attempted to image M101 before the supernova, but had moved on when I couldn't see any spiral arms after a two minute exposure? This short exposure after post processing is shown below. Admittedly it's actually a nice image for only two minutes, too bad I didn't stay on this target for say 20 minutes before going on to image the supernova 2023dtz.

For the **BIG SURPRISE**, turn to the next page.

“Pinwheel” spiral galaxy **M101** in Ursa Major
with new type II supernova **2023ixf**
reported 19 May 2023 at mag 14.9
First SN in M101 in 12 years!

M101
dist ~ 6.4 Mpc
~ 21 Mly
mag ~ 7.9

10:31 pm Eastern
21 May 2023
15x8sG540
SN **2023ixf** mag ~ 11.4
my actual 1st SN image

So, let's see if we can summarize this most strange night of observing at TAO.

Initially there was so much haze and smoke in the sky that I was unable to see even Polaris. Around 9:40 pm, without alignment, I slewed down to the crescent moon "by hand" to capture a few single-frame millisecond-scale lunar images.

Polaris became visible just before 10 pm, so I next aligned my scope starting with Polaris, using about 8 bright stars. I then pointed the OTA at M101, the "Pinwheel galaxy" in Ursa Major, hoping for a few nice bright galaxy images. I took a short 2-minute live stack image of M101, but it appeared to lack detail; I was unhappy with it, and thought the problem might be more haze in the sky.

After M101 I had planned to move to a faint supernova, and capture my first ever supernova image. I chose the supernova 2023dtz in Coma Berenices, and captured a 20 minute live stack of the host galaxy NGC 4611 and field stars. Fortunately, this part of the sky was clearer; this image showed SN 2023dtz, which had faded to approximately mag 16.8, but was still clearly visible, near the nucleus of NGC 4611. Success!

However this was NOT my first image of a supernova. Unbeknownst to me, a supernova had gone off in M101 just two days earlier (as seen from Earth), the first observed in that galaxy in 12 years, and it was now the brightest supernova in the sky! I had accidentally captured a nice image of this new, bright supernova, 2023ixf without realizing that it was there, before moving on to the much fainter SN 2023dtz. So, I did capture my first supernova image that night, as planned, but it was not the faint one that I expected. It was instead the totally unexpected bright new headline-grabbing supernova 2023ixf !

Finally I managed a 16 minute live stack (120x8sG540) of galaxy NGC 3310 in UMa, which had sounded promising but was indistinct and covered a small angular area. It was then 11:49 pm and most people were departing or had already departed, so I packed up and left, followed soon after by Don Spong.

At the time it had seemed an unsuccessful evening, with mediocre sky conditions that were well below expectations, and yet I returned from TAO with a crescent moon and my first two supernovae.

Dr. Barnes at TAO,
catching photons from extragalactic supernovae.
21 May 2023

Equipment Summary for Astrophotography

Don's Equipment:

My standard equipment is a Celestron 8" Edge HD telescope and a Celestron AVX mount. I supplement the f10 Edge HD scope with two focal length reducers: a 0.7 reducer (f7) and a Starizona Hyperstar attachment, which replaces the secondary mirror and gets me down to a very bright f1.9. Focusing is controlled with a ZWO electronic automatic focuser that is attached to the Celestron. I also have two refractors that I sometimes use: a Sky Watcher Pro ED doublet 80mm refractor and an Apertura 72mm refractor (travel scope). Imaging and mount are controlled by a ZWO ASIAIR, generally run in Live Stacking Mode, although in the past I've also used Celestron's CWPI software for mount control. My main camera is a ZWO 183 MC Pro in Bin1 mode (5496 x 3672 pixels), usually cooled down to -20 deg. C. The guide scope is an ORION 60mm with a ZWO 120MM mini monochrome camera. Processing done with PixInsight and Lightroom.

Ted's Equipment:

My standard equipment is a 190mm Orion Maksutov-Newtonian telescope (which has very nice optics), a Celestron CGX mount, a ZWO ASI294MC-P cooled color camera, a ZWO motorized five-position filter wheel, an Orion 50mm guide scope with a ZWO ASI290MM-mini camera and PHD2 guiding software, and a laser pointer attached to the OTA for when I am totally "lost in space." For alignment and mount control I use CPWI Telescope Control Software v.2.4.2, and SharpCap v.4.0 for image capture, all software (PHD2, CPWI and SharpCap) running on a refurbished Dell Win10 Pro laptop with an external 24" diagonal ASUS monitor. I also use sheets of 1/8" thick rigid dark red plastic for my PC screen and ASUS monitor, to protect night vision. For post processing I use Windows Live Photo Gallery, which suffices for my needs, and to extract image coordinates I use the All-Sky Plate Solver program (ASPS). To access Gaia data and other "serious" astronomical databases I recommend the French CDS interactive sky atlas Aladin (currently v.11). Finally, for planning observing sessions and locating somewhat faint asteroids I find the real-time sky simulation program TheSkyX to be very helpful.

Astronomy

Some numbers are quoted to 4 place accuracy where appropriate.

1 parsec (pc) = 3.262 light years (ly)

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = 63 241 AU

1 AU = 149 597 870.7 km *exactly*

c = speed of light = 299 792 458 m/s *exactly* = 1 ly/yr. ☺

1 yr (Julian) = 365.25 d *exactly* = 31 557 600 s *exactly*

1 d = 86 400 s *exactly*

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly

distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 10 kpc

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m

H_{alpha} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 1 change in magnitude = $10^{2/5} \sim 2.512$ x fainter

+ 2.5 change in mag = 10 x fainter

+ 5 change in mag = 100 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = 100 x fainter = + 5 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness if seen from a distance of 10 pc

M_{abs} (our Sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm² sec (Barnes's rule ☺)

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = angle around the celestial polar axis,
in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = angle above the celestial equator,
in degrees, minutes, and seconds (° ' "); analogous to latitude.

RA and Dec, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's
direction in the sky.

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = total days that have passed since noon UT
on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC.

Meeting ORION:

Rob Fowler

In this new feature, each month we will hear from an ORION member regarding their background, career, interests, and attraction to astronomy. We are grateful to Rob Fowler, our videographer, for kindly agreeing to provide our first contribution.

Born in NY, I was raised in central NJ, about halfway between Trenton and Philadelphia. I can still remember when you could see the Milky Way from my front yard. As a kid, I was interested in all things science. I found Star Trek early on and was lucky enough to attend some of those early fan-driven Star Trek conventions. At 7, my father helped me purchase my first telescope, a 3-inch reflector from Edmund Scientific. The things he gave me as gifts encouraged my interests; a microscope, and various electronic kits, *etc.*

But in 1979, my dad pulled off what I now refer to as “standard Dad trick #1.” He bought a computer for himself and refused to let me touch it for the first few days. I was only allowed to watch him use it. The second week, I could use it, but only if he was present. By the third week, I was beginning to learn BASIC. A few months later, he asked me to move the computer onto my desk as it was “in his way on his desk.” I didn't realize until years later, but he had given me one of the most expensive and valuable gifts of my life; a love of programming.

All of my other interests took a back seat. That summer, I totally immersed myself in programming. When the fall arrived and it was time to go back to school I began my first class in programming. But the instructor, who had only just begin learning BASIC himself, soon realized that I was more advanced than he was. So he let me work on my own projects instead of sitting through the lectures.

Religion: It was around 1980, that I became interested in acquiring wisdom and I believed instinctively, the place to look was the Bible. I immersed myself in every religious broadcast that I could find. Slowly over time, that crowd thinned as I noticed the discrepancies between some and the pointing finger among others. The following year, I joined a local church and began volunteering as a sound tech. I went on to do that for about 20 years.

In 1988 I had one of the most unusual experiences of my life. I went to work for a Christian ministry for 1 year traveling with a small production company. They performed a play called “The Greatest Star of All,” an allegory designed to present the gospel to children. I was hired as the sound and lighting tech. It wasn't the most profitable period of my life, but I wouldn't trade those experiences for anything.

Two years later, I attended Full Sail Center for the Recording Arts where I earned an Associated Degree in Recording Engineering and Live Sound Reinforcement.

Career: I tried lots of things before achieving any success in my career. I even did some freelancing as a programmer for a few months. But my first career job was as computer operator for Pathmark, a Northeastern supermarket chain. Pathmark is no more but it was a serious contender in its day.

After Full Sail, and a few years working at a wedding video shop, I eventually ended up at Bristol Myers Squibb as an audiovisual technician, and stayed for 10 years. I was now applying much of what I learned at Full Sail, both audio and video production. I was there at a very lucky time, just when the kinds of things AV supported suddenly became necessary at every meeting. The amount of money that was poured in to equipment and staff was startling and we felt valued.

I had 2 short-term temp positions at the Princeton Plasma Physics Lab, totaling 16 months. The work and the people we served were delightful, and I would probably still be there now if they ever offered me a permanent position. But after the end of the second term, I decided it was finally time to move south. I picked Oak Ridge because of the proximity of ORNL, in hopes that I would one day get a job there. And because of Windrock Park. There is just about nothing I enjoy more than getting on the back of an ATV and riding up into the mountains. I discovered I have a great memory for trails; a knack for navigation.

Astronomy: I distinctly remember the first time I saw Saturn and its rings, or Jupiter and its moons. I considered the photons and the immense distance they covered before ending up at my eye. But right along side of that, I also remember the hours of frustration I experienced trying point that reflector to see them, or anything else of interest. So I really didn't pull my telescope out very often. Even the fuzzy smudge of the Orion Nebula didn't do anything for me.

But one day around 2007, I pointed my DSLR at the Orion Nebula and took a 2-second exposure. Suddenly there was shape and color! This ability to see things that I couldn't see at all with the naked eye fascinated me, and revitalized my interest in Astronomy. I found a Celestron 70AZ at a thrift store for \$35, and found that it was much easier to use than my \$200 reflector.

After moving to Tennessee in 2016, I thought a great way to meet current and former ORNL employees would be to find a local astronomy club. So I found ORION. Through ORION, I got to know a good friend, Dr. David Fields, who introduced me to John Preston and John Rather. John Preston helped me get involved with the Interstellar Research Group, where I continue to do lots of freelance videography and video editing work. Dr John Rather has become a great friend and mentor, and has also given me lots of work on his various videos, meetings and presentations.

I am currently working outside of my chosen career field and am actively seeking full-time employment in any position that does not require long periods of standing, or long distances of walking.

Public Stargazing at TAO

We especially wish to invite the public to attend the public stargazing events usually held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee.

The dates and times of these events depend on local weather and sky conditions, and accordingly cannot be specified long in advance. They will however often be within a few days of the New Moon. Once a date is chosen we announce it through the ORION email list, ORIONastronomy@groups.io. One may subscribe to this list.

Some special instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with the etiquette associated with stargazing at a dark-sky site.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, "Observatory Way," all first time visitors should drive to the site before dark. Directions may be found at:

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their binoculars and / or telescopes, to prepare for evening observing and share refreshments. Please consider bringing a red flashlight, or a headband with a red light.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or headbands for visiting may find them at many commercial astronomy sites, such as

<https://www.highpointscientific.com>

and even Amazon. A personal favorite (from Amazon, for about \$20), is the Lighting Ever company's LED Headlamp Model No. 3200008, which is rechargeable using a mini USB cable, and has separate red and white buttons. A caution, for astronomy events, brighter LEDs are NOT better. Many manufacturers appear to be unaware of this.

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up telescopes and astrophotography equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are also welcome to refreshments, including coffee, which is available in the TAO main building.

